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Electromagnetic fields in manufacturing and living locations and modern instruments for their detection

Currently larger interest causes the problem of health and the defences of humans, as to the gender of its work or activity durable residing under the exposure of electromagnetic fields (EMF) on its workstation, in shielding natural EMF hermetic closely subtly and thick-walled locations (in planes, in space apparata, in marine ships, in closely military technician, in underground constructions, in metro and etc.). For example, on marine ships crew long time resides and works in the shielding location conditions, in conditions so-called "hypomagnetic fields" (HMF), namely in conditions the superposition of constant fields created of weakened geomagnetic field, of the fields of the ferromagnetic parts of the construction of ship and fields created of constant currents, flowing as to these constructions. That is why here arised the problem of permissible hygienic norms and demands to the crew workstation.

Durable exposure of HMF on man brings to reduction it efficiency, to negative action on his health. Such fields are biologic active factor causing a number of changes on physiological, biochemical and the morphologic levels of organism functioning.

Knownly, what main of HMF indicators are: the intensity of the vector of constant magnetic field inside of location, the corner of the inclination of this vector inside of location and the gradient of the magnetic field intensity between two points in space inside of locations.

Investigations showed, what biologic frontier, divisive safe and the harmful conditions of labor at presence of the HMF is characterize the coefficient of it weakening concerning the natural magnetic field of open space equal 2. Is establish, what at weakening of HMF in 2... 5 times concerning natural magnetic field, is seen increasing on 40% the number of diseases at humans working in the conditions of such locations. At the man's are found in artificial hypomagnetic conditions are marked of psychology changes, emerge nonstandard ideas, images.

For electromagnetic examinations in the locations of any type and dimensions are created modern intellectual magnetometers (IM) on the

basis of amorphous fluxgates which let to conduct of rooms certification, their mapping, the definition of the harmful sources of radiation. At help the IM emerged possibility to develop the estimation criterions of EMF and HMF in locations. Below are presented the main characteristics of the IM created in IZMIRAN (Institute of Terrestrial Magnetism, Ionosphere and Radiowave Propagation of RAS) in recent years.

INDICATOR OF ELECTROMAGNETIC SITUATION MAGIC MF-06 is a hand-held instrument with built-in sensor and by digital indicator allowing to define the sources of the harmful electromagnetic radiations of artificial origin according exposure to man on his workstation, on transport, and also to carry out the monitoring of the level of electromagnetic situation in electronic industry, in local and hypomagnetic rooms.

The ranges of constant magnetic fields measurement: 2, 20 and 200 mT. Sensitivity of digital indicator accordingly 1, 10 and 100 nT. Accuracy not above 1%. Power source 9 V from the 6F22 battery. Power consumption in autonomous regime not above 0.12 W. Is provided power supply from AC 220 V, by frequency 50 Hz at the help of standard networked adapter and the analog signal delivery on analog recorder (0...2,5 V). The device dimensions are 160x65x25 mm, weight is not above 0.15 kg.

INDICATOR OF ELECTROMAGNETIC SITUATION IDL-08 is a hand-held instrument with built-in graphic indicator allowing visualized the offsprings of the electromagnetic situation examination in local room in the form the building of magnetic maps and three-dimensional view in a moment of measured fields, in process or at termination conducting of examinations.

The measurement range of the constant magnetic fields is 200 mT. Accuracy of graphic indicator at the building of magnetic maps is 0.1 mT. Power consumption in autonomous regime is not above 0.45 W. Is provided for power supply from AC 220 V, by frequency 50 Hz at the help of standard networked adapter and the data transmission on PC through consecutive port. The instruments weight is not above 0.5 kg.

INDICATOR OF ELECTROMAGNETIC SITUATION MAGIC MAF-08 is appointed for the definition of frequency and the amplitudes of the sources of the harmful electromagnetic radiation of artificial origin according exposure to man, in frequency range from 5 Hz till 100 kHz.

The measurement range of variable EMF: 0... 200 mT. Accuracy in measuring range is not above 5%. Power supply is 9 V from the 6F22 battery. Power consumption in autonomous regime is not above 0.15 W. Dimensions of device are 140x82x36 mm and its weight is not above 0.25 kg.

INDICATOR OF ELECTROMAGNETIC SITUATION IDL-10 is a hand-held instrument with built-in graphic indicator allowing visualized the results of the examination of electromagnetic situation in local room in the form the building of spectrum measured the EMF in real time scale. Lets to conduct the attestation of manufacturing locations and workstation with

computer technology.

The measurement range of variable EMF: 0...200 mkT. Accuracy of graphic indicator is 1%. Power consumption in autonomous regime is not above 0.35 W. Power supply realized from accumulator battery is provided for power supply from AC 220 V, by frequency 50 Hz at the help of standard networked adapter and the transmission of digital information on PC through consecutive port. The weight of instrument is not above 0.5 kg.

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